

Automated Tagging of Image and Video Collections using Face Recognition

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The Goal

- Provide TAGs or retrieve frames in videos using face recognition
- Two example datasets

The BFI Untagged dataset

Tags: ?

Film: "Slumdog Millionaire"

The BBC News dataset

Tags: ?

Programme: "Newsnight"

Visual Challenges for Face Recognition

- Performing this task using **Face Recognition** can be challenging

Age

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Viewpoint

The Approach

1. Detect Faces

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2. Represent each face by a vector

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For this to work, need vectors to only represent **identity**, and not be affected by expression, pose, lighting, age, etc

Basic workhorse - face to vector

- Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) deep architecture

SE-ResNet-50-256D architecture with 30M parameters

J. Hu, L. Shen, G. Sun, "Squeeze-and-Excitation Networks", IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, 2018

Trained on the VGGFace2 dataset

Face Dataset (VGGFace2)

- **3M+** face images, **300+** images for each of **9000** identities

Q. Cao, L. Shen, W. Xie, O. M. Parkhi, A. Zisserman, "VGGFace2: A dataset for recognising faces across pose and age", International Conference on Automatic Face and Gesture Recognition, 2018

(a) John Wesley Shipp

(e) Roy Jones Jr.

(b) Leymah Gbowee

(f) Ruby Lin

(c) Princess Haya Bint Al Hussein

(g) Additi Gupta

(d) Julio Cesar Chavez Jr.

(h) Lee Jun-gi

Basic workhorse - face to vector

- Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) deep architecture

Once the network is trained, it can be used to generate feature vectors for previously unseen people

Automatic Tagging Example

- The British Film Institute provided us with
 - Names of **11K people** of interest
 - Metadata for movies/tv-shows (title, year) and their cast

Tags: ?

Film: "Four Weddings and a Funeral"

- **GOAL:** Provide tags for these 11K people on dataset with **46K images**

Tagging the images

Obtaining identity images

- Use web image search engines (e.g. Google)
 - Works well for “famous” people (~**6.5K** in the dataset)
 - Can automatically determine if famous or not using clustering

Displaying the image ranking

- Results are ordered starting from the best at the top-left corner
- Location of the detected face can be highlighted

Text query: Meryl Streep

Rank:

1

2

3

4

5

Rank:

6

7

8

9

The BFI Browser

- Provides functionality to search for people by name or by movie/tv-show title
- Filter results by “featured” or “non-featured” in the credits

Anomalies Found

1. Images labelled with the wrong film

e.g. all of the images from "War Horse" were labelled as being from "Anterior and Posterior Plaster Beds"

The Labelled Film Name: "Anterior and Posterior Plaster Beds" – 1936

Correct Film Name: "War Horse" - 2011

Steven Spielberg is tagged in this image, but is not in the cast/crew

Anomalies Found

2. Actors/actresses left out of the cast/crew

Geraldine Somerville left out of the cast of "Cracker" (TV series)

Donald Sutherland left out of the cast of "Commander in Chief" (TV series)

Anomalies Found

3. People appearing on sets when they are not in the cast/crew

Marilyn Monroe appears in
"Ritz" (Film)

Sharon Stone appears on
"Richard & Judy" (TV Series)

Tony Blair appears on
"Richard & Judy" (TV Series)

1,821 anomalies identified in total across the dataset

The decision of whether an anomaly is a mislabelling or a surprise appearance **can be done automatically**

Face Recognition on Video Data

- The BBC News Search system performs visual searches over a large video dataset (~10K hours of video, ~5M keyframes, ~1.5 TB)
- Four search categories are available, including **People**

Video Demo

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the address bar containing "127.0.0.1/bbc_search1/". The page features a prominent red header with the text "BBC NEWS SEARCH" in white, bold letters. Below this, it states "powered by Oxford's Visual Geometry Group". A navigation bar includes a "Sign in" link in the top right and four menu items: "Instances", "Objects/Scenes", "Text", and "People". A search input field contains the text "search term/image" and is accompanied by a dropdown menu currently set to "BBC News" and a search icon. Below the search bar, a section titled "Why not try?" offers suggestions: "mona lisa", "buckingham palace", and "coca cola". Three small image thumbnails are displayed below these suggestions, each with a yellow bounding box highlighting a specific object. The first thumbnail shows a doorway, the second shows the word "Google" on a wall, and the third shows a Manchester United player. In the bottom right corner, there is a logo for the "UNIVERSITY OF OXFORD Visual Geometry Group" and a link labeled "Getting Started".

Automatic Tagging in News videos

- Similarly to the BFI browser, we could pre-generate lists of results where specific people appears

The image shows a screenshot of a video search interface. On the left, a large video frame shows a man in a suit and tie sitting at a desk. A white arrow points from this frame to a search bar in the top right. The search bar contains the text "03487.jpg" and has a magnifying glass icon. To the right of the search bar are icons for a grid, a film strip, and a video camera. Below the search bar, there are tabs for "Instances", "Objects/Scenes", "Text", and "People". The "People" tab is selected. A "Next >" button is located to the right of the tabs. Below the search bar, the text "Search results page 1 of 100 (5,000 results)" is displayed. The search results are presented in a grid of 15 video thumbnails, arranged in three rows of five. Each thumbnail shows the same man in a suit and tie sitting at a desk, in various poses and settings. Below each thumbnail is a small icon of a film strip and the text "Newsnight".

Extensions: Compound Queries

- Retrieve frames containing both a target **face** and a target **scene**

Query: "Barack Obama in the Office"

BBC NEWS
SEARCH

Next >

Search results page 1 of 4 (200 results)

World News Today

BBC Weekend News

BBC News

BBC News

BBC News

Newsnight

Obama The Interview

BBC News

BBC News

BBC News

BBC News

BBC News

BBC News at Six

Newsnight

BBC News at Ten

Extensions: Compound Queries

- Retrieve frames containing **multiple people**

Query:	Query:	Query:
<p data-bbox="476 660 578 686">Top 5:</p>		

More information and demos at
<http://www.robots.ox.ac.uk/~vgg/>

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